

X-Ray Diffractogram- SAIF Kochi

XZNO (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

2Theta

Sample ID	XZNO
File Name	SAIFXR-19410-240529-02(XZNO).raw (Smooth)
Scan Type	Coupled TwoTheta/Theta
Scan Mode	Continouusscan
Start	10.000 °
End	80.003 °
Step Size	0.020 °
Total Time/Step	57.60 s
Temperature	25 °C (Room)
Goniometer Radius	280.0 mm
Sample Rotation	0.000 1/min
Anode	Cu
$k\alpha_2$ Ratio	0.50000
Wavelength for display	1.54060 Å
Generator kV	40.0 kV
Generator mA	35.0 mA
Detector Opening	2.947 °
Air-Scatter Screen Mode	Automatic
Divergence Slit	15 mm
Antiscatter Slit	18.000
Compute Crystallinity	No
%-Crystallinity	
%-Amorphous	
Global Area	